

STUDIES ON THE NATURE OF HUMUS AND CLAY-HUMUS COMPLEX

By H. MUKERJEE

The acidic character of humus is attributed to the presence of both phenolic and carboxylic groups. The adsorption of humus by clay suspensions has been found to be enhanced in presence of metal ions, and a portion of the adsorbed humus cannot be extracted by alkali.

Humus is known to be adsorbed by clay particles, but the exact mechanism of this adsorption is not clearly understood. Humus is considered to be polybasic due to the presence of carboxylic and phenolic groups. Gillam (*Soil Sci.*, 1944, **40**, 433) showed that by methylating humus and thus rendering the OH groups non-functional, the total acidity as well as the buffer capacity of humus was reduced. To elucidate the structure of clay-humus complexes, Mayers (*ibid.*, 1937, **44**, 331) and Sideri (*ibid.*, 1936, **42**, 461; 1938, **46**, 267) studied respectively the mixed clay-humus suspensions by viscometric and optical method under the polarising microscope. These investigations show that as a result of adsorption, large-sized clay-humus micelles are formed in which the majority of the clay particles possess a fairly definite orientation.

The present investigation deals with studies of the nature of humus isolated from a soil and with an understanding of the clay-humus complex from several standpoints.

In the experiments described below, the adsorption of the original as well as methylated humus by H- and Ca-clay suspensions has been studied and changes in the b.e.c. of the clay have been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methylation of Humus.—Humus was extracted from a sample of black cotton soil from Bombay by treating 100 g. of it with a litre of 0.5N-Na₂CO₃ solution and then siphoning off after 48 hours the supernatant liquid containing sodium humate. Humic acid was precipitated by acidifying with HCl and finally purified by electro-dialysis.

Humic acid was methylated according to Gillam (*loc. cit.*). To about 5% suspension of humic acid (100 c.c.) in water, taken in a vessel, 50% solution of KOH (10 c.c.) was added and the vessel was kept surrounded by cold water while the mixture was kept agitated with dropwise addition of dimethyl sulphate (20 c.c.). The suspension was kept alkaline during the course of the reaction by a further addition of KOH (15 c.c.). Stirring was continued for 2 hours and the flask was kept on a water-bath at 60° for 2 hours. After standing overnight, the suspension was poured into a large volume of cold water containing sufficient sulphuric acid to precipitate the methylated humus. The methylated humus was then electro-dialysed to remove the electrolytes and to convert it into the H-form.

The humus contents of the original soil as well as the methylated product were estimated by the method of Walkley and Black (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1933, 25, 498) for the determination of the organic matter in soil. The methoxyl content was determined by the Micro-Zeisel method (Pregl, "Die quantitative Organische Microanalyse", 3rd Ed., 1930, pp. 198-215).

The titrations of humic acid and of the methylated product were carried out potentiometrically using 0.1N-NaOH solution. The methylated humus did not form a stable suspension, and hence, after each addition of alkali, the mixture was vigorously stirred. Near about p_H 7.0, the suspension became fairly stable. The adsorption experiments described below had to be done with this stabilised suspension.

The electro dialysed clay fraction ($<0.5\mu$), isolated from a sample of Kashmir bentonite, was used in the experiments described below. This fraction has a b.e.c. = 113 m.e./100 g. and consists of montmorillonite alone.

The adsorption was studied in the following way. Mixtures of clay soil and the humus suspension were taken in stoppered bottles in the desired proportions, then shaken in a mechanical shaker for 6 hours and kept overnight. The unadsorbed humus was removed by washing with water in the filter paper and the total washings were analysed.

The base exchange capacity (b.e.c.) of the treated clay was determined by the half-saturated KCl method (Ganguli, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 1417). Slight antagonism which may occur in systems containing two dissimilar valency ions, e.g. in the titration of Ca-clay—humic acid mixtures with NaOH, has been ignored.

To a portion of the washed clay-humus complex 0.5N-Na₂CO₃ solution (25 c.c.) was added, the mixture shaken for 6 hours and filtered. The residue was washed with water till free of humus. The amount of humus in the entire filtrate was determined according to Walkley and Black's method (*loc. cit.*). The results are shown in Tables I-III.

TABLE I

Adsorption of humus and the methylated product by H- and Ca-clays

System.	Wt. of humic acid per 100 g. clay.	p_H of the mixture.	Humic acid adsorbed per 100 g. of clay.	B.e.c. of the clay-humus complex (in m.e./100 g.)
H-clay—humic acid	2 g.	3.8	1.5 g.	94
	4	3.6	2.9	92
	8	3.4	5.1	90
	10	3.3	5.3	90
Ca-clay—humic acid	2	6.6	1.6	10
	4	6.4	3.2	13
	8	5.8	7.1	18
	10	5.5	9.0	15
H-clay—methylated acid	2	4.80	1.30	16
	4	4.95	2.36	12
	8	4.90	3.04	12
	10	5.10	3.90	10
Ca-clay—methylated acid	2	7.20	1.3	
	4	7.15	2.0	
	8	7.2	5.2	
	10	7.1	5.3	

TABLE II

Substance.	% Carbon (with ash).	B. e. c. in m. e./100 g. (from inflexions).	Methoxyl content.
Humic acid	46.25	640	Nil
Methylated humic acid	48.56	260	10.97%

TABLE III

Estimation of alkali-extractable humus and the methylated product.

System.	Humic acid. per 100 g. of clay.		Adsorbed humic acid recovered.
	Added.	Adsorbed.	
H-clay—humic acid	10 g.	5.3 g.	79.6%
Ca-clay—humic acid	10	9.0	76.4
H-clay—methylated humus	10	3.9	57.9
Ca-clay—methylated humus	10	5.3	56.2

DISCUSSION

The acidic behaviour of the phenolic groups present in humus is shown by the titration curves as well as the calculated values of b.e.c. (Table II). A considerable fall in b.e.c. occurs as a result of methylation of the phenolic groups.

FIG. 1
Effect of KCl on the titration curves of humic & methylated humic acids.

FIG. 2
Titration curves of humic acid and the methylated product.

The diminution of b.e.c. of the methylated product indirectly shows the contribution of the phenolic groups towards the b.e.c. of the original material. Unlike clay acids, titration in presence of KCl shows only a slight increase in b.e.c. of humus and the methylated product. This is probably due to a greater percentage availability of H ions of humus neutralisation by alkalis than that in the case of clay acids. Working with

humic acid sols Chatterjee and Bose (*J. Coll. Sci.*, 1952, 1, 414) observed similar increase in b.e.c. in presence of neutral salts. The increase was greater (about 10 and 20%) in the case of NaOH—NaCl and Ba(OH)₂—BaCl₂ systems studied by them, but almost negligible in the case of Ca(OH)₂—CaCl₂ systems. No indication is, however, obtained of the different inflexions due to carboxyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups. Most likely the degree of dissociation of these two groups in humus is not wide enough to show two inflexions.

FIG. 3

Effect of concentration of humic acid and its methylated product on their adsorption by H and Ca-clay.

The adsorption of humus and its methylated product is increased with increasing concentration, and it reaches an almost limiting value. The higher values of adsorption of humus by the Ca-clay than the H-clay is due to the fact that Ca ions are more capable than H ions of forming strong co-ordination bonds with the OH and -COOH groups of humus acid and clay anion. A similar strong co-ordination has been shown in the case of interaction of Krilium (a poly-acrylonitrile) and Ca-clay (Mukherjee, *J. Ind. Soil Sci. Soc.*, 1954, 2, 95). That the OH groups of humus play an important part in forming co-ordination bond is shown by the considerably decreased adsorption of methylated humus by Ca-clay.

The values of the exchangeable H ions of the clay, humus complexes reveal several interesting points. The high b.e.c. of the H-clay—humus complexes is due to H ions of clay as well as those of phenolic and carboxylic groups of humus.

It is likely that in the Ca-clay—humus complex, most of the OH groups form co-ordination bonds with Ca ions. The bonding is so strong that the OH groups are no longer capable of donating the protons, and consequently Ca-clay—humus complex

records considerably lower values of b.e.c. For the same reason, the b.e.c. of the methylated H-clay-humus complex is low since in the latter the phenolic groups are absent, and moreover, the major proportion of the carboxylic groups must have already been neutralised by alkali when the methylated humus is treated with NaOH for stabilising its suspension. Ca-clay-methylated humus system also possesses no exchange acidity. In no case has the b.e.c. of the clay-humus complex been found to be additive. This might suggest a possible interaction of the clay with the humus.

The data in Table III show that a portion of the adsorbed humus is not extractable by alkali which has also been observed by Khan (*Pedology*, U.S.S.R., 1950, 673; *Doklady Akad. Nauk*, U.S.S.R., 1951, 81, 461). This non-extractable portion is greater in the case of methylated humus, and also slightly higher when Ca ions are present. This suggests that the COOH groups form stronger bonding than OH groups and metal ions are more effective in strong bond-formation than H ions. Further, it is seen that there must be two types of linkage between clay and humus: one is a weak bonding corresponding to the alkali-extractable portion, and another is strong bonding corresponding to the alkali-non-extractable portion. Perhaps the weakly bound humus is present as a coating on the outermost surface of the clay micelle and strongly bound portion is held by ions present in the crystal lattice.

The author's thanks are due to Dr. S. K. Mukherjee, D. Sc., Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University, for his guidance and providing laboratory facilities.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

Received November 19, 1955.